

Perceptions of Educational Environment among Undergraduate Medical Students in a Tertiary Institution in South-East Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Educational environment involves all learning activities between students and teachers including physical facilities in the institutions.

Objectives: This study aimed at assessing the medical students' perceptions of their learning environment in Ebonyi State University Abakaliki, Nigeria with a view to improving the quality of medical education. **Methods:** This was a cross-sectional study among 344 medical students from second to sixth year selected by stratified sampling method. Dundee Ready Educational Environment Measures (DREEM) inventory which is composed of five domains was applied to assess the various aspects of effective educational environment. Statistical analyses (proportions and mean score percentages) were carried out using IBM-SPSS version 25 software. **Results:** One hundred and eighty three (53.2%) were male respondents and 161 (46.8%) female respondents. The mean age was 22.4 ± 2.9 years with 67(19.5%) students in second year, 95(27.6%) in the third year, 65(18.9%) in the fourth year, 51(14.8%) in the fifth year and 66(19.2%) in the sixth year. The mean global perception in our study was 102.4/200 points (51.2%). Scores for students' academic self perception (SASP), students' perception of learning (SPL) and students' social self perception (SSSP) were 20.7/32 (64.6%), 27.7/48 (57.8%), 16.6/28 (51.8%) respectively. Two key areas needed attention: students' perception of course organizers (SPCO) and students' perception of atmosphere (SPA) which were 20.9/44 (47.6%) and 16.4/48 (34.2%) respectively. **Conclusion:** Improvement is needed in some aspect of teaching and atmosphere. This will further be of benefit to medical students and their training as well as the performance.

Key words: Learning environment, medical students, perceptions

INTRODUCTION

Education is a learning process that increases people's knowledge and awareness about environment and associated challenges. It makes for development of the necessary skills and expertise to address challenges and foster attitudes, innovations and commitments to make informed

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Journal Metrics:

Website: www.jbmcs.org.ng

E-mail: editor.jbmcs@gmail.com

Article Metrics:

Date Submitted: 20 June 2022

Date Accepted: 19 Sept. 2022

Date Published: 6 Nov. 2022

Publisher:

cPrint, Nig. Ltd

E-mail: cprintpublisher@gmail.com

How to cite this article

Bernard I Ituma, Elizabeth U Nwonwu, Anthony C Onyeka, Sunday B Agbom, Christianus O Nwaduru. Perceptions of Educational Environment among Undergraduate Medical Students in a Tertiary Institution in South-East Nigeria. *J Bas Med Clin Sci*: 2022;1(1):39-46. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7275123

Access to the article

Website: <http://www.jbmcs.org.ng>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7275123

decisions and take responsible actions.¹ Educational environment involves all teaching-learning activities between students and teachers including physical facilities in the institutions. It is primarily affected by the curriculum which consists of all events in the classroom, department, faculty, medical school or the university as a whole.²

Quality of medical school graduates is influenced by cumulative effect of their learning environment.³ Students' perception of educational environment significantly impact their academic progress and sense of wellbeing. A physician's level of competence to a certain extent depends on the educational institution they attended and medical education they received.⁴ It is therefore important to appraise the educational environment in which medical students learn including institutional culture, curriculum and learning climate.

In the complex and unique environment of courses like medicine and surgery, students experience many interactions with multi-professional staff, peers and even strangers.⁵ They have a heavy academic workload and are required to conform to professional norms of behaviours.⁶ The atmosphere in schools is often competitive and sometimes hostile. Students may feel humiliated and even abused in the course of their learning. A combination of lectures and clinical exposures is common in medical training. There is scarcity of empirical evidence that evaluates this current balance or the way its delivery is perceived by Nigerian medical students. The lack of empirical research means little is known about the way medical students perceive their course learning environment. Hence this study aimed to determine students' perceptions of various areas of their learning environment in College of Medicine, Ebonyi State University Abakaliki, south-east Nigeria and areas that needs adequate attention in order to improve learning among students as well as their mental and social wellbeing. This study will also serve as a baseline assessment of students' perceptions of their educational environment and for comparison in the future.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Setting: We studied medical students of College of Medicine, Ebonyi State University Abakaliki. It is made up of faculty of basic medical sciences in the second and third levels of study, faculty of basic clinical sciences in the fourth level and faculty of clinical medicine (fifth and sixth levels).

Study Design, Population and Sample Size: This was a descriptive cross-sectional study among medical students of the university. The eligibility criteria are medical students who had completed at least one full academic session in the university. The first year medical students were excluded from the study. This category of students are likely to be excited at gaining admission to medical school and may not have stayed long enough to adequately and objectively respond to the various components of the DREEM questionnaire. They are also considered to be students in the faculty of science and do not live in the same residential area as other higher medical students. Including them in the study will introduce some level of bias. The appropriate sample size for a single proportion ($n = z^2 pq/d^2$) was used to calculate the sample size. A total of 344 medical students were recruited for the study based on type 1 error (α) of 0.05, a tolerable error margin of 0.05 and a prevalence of 54.2% representing the proportion of medical students with positive perception of their learning environment in Ilorin, Kwara State Nigeria.³

Sampling Technique and Study Instrument: The respondents were selected by stratified sampling method. The study population was 660 excluding first year medical students, 128 in second year, 182 in third year, 125 in fourth year, 98 in fifth year and 127 in sixth year. Each class served as a stratum. Proportional allocation was applied to each stratum as follows: second year, $128/660 \times 344$ (sample size) = 67; third year, $182/660 \times 344 = 95$; fourth year, $125/660 \times 344 = 65$; fifth year, $98/660 \times 344 = 51$, and sixth year, $127/660 \times 344 = 66$. Simple random sampling by balloting method was applied to each class/stratum to select the 344 study participants. The study instrument

was semi-structured questionnaire which consisted of two sections: socio-demographic characteristics of students (questions 1 -12) and Dundee Ready Educational Environment Measure (DREEM) which was composed of five domains (questions 13 - 62). The major domains in the questionnaire measured specifically relevant areas in assessing education environment. The five areas are students' academic self perception (SASP), 8 items with a maximum score of 32; students' perception of learning (SPL), 12 items with a maximum score of 48; students' social self perception (SSSP), 7 items with a maximum score of 28; students' perception of course organizers (SPCO), 11 items with maximum score of 44, and students' perception of atmosphere (SPA), 12 items with maximum score of 48.

Responses to the DREEM assessment were on a five point likert scale, each item is scored from 0 to 4 (strongly disagree = 0, disagree = 1, unsure = 2, agree = 3, strongly agree = 4). The nine negatively worded items (numbers 20, 24, 27, 28, 33, 37, 53, 58, 62) were reversely scored. Agreement or disagreement with individual items was calculated by combining agree (A) and strongly agree (SA) categories, and disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD) categories respectively. The mean score percentage was calculated as follows: $\frac{\text{sum (A + SA) or (D + SD)}}{\text{number of items in the domain} \times \text{sample size}}$ expressed in percentage.⁷ The maximum overall DREEM assessment was 200 indicating an ideal education environment.

The DREEM questionnaire is widely used and validated for assessing education environment. The internal consistency of the questionnaire has been validated in previous studies.^{3,8} Questionnaires were sorted after data collection to identify the ones correctly and completely filled and these were included in the study. Incompletely filled questionnaire were excluded from analysis. Data were analyzed using IBM-SPSS version 25 software and significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the research and ethics committee of Alex Ekwueme Federal University

Teaching Hospital Abakaliki (AEFUTHA/REC/VOL.3/2021/160). We obtained a written informed consent from the medical students before questionnaire administration. The respondents were made to know that participation in the study was voluntary and assured that information obtained will be treated anonymously and with confidentiality.

RESULTS

The mean age was 22.4 ± 2.9 years. Among the students, in the study 67(19.5%) were in their second year of study, 95 (27.6%) in third year, 65 (18.9%) in fourth year, 51 (14.8%) in fifth year and 66 (19.2%) in sixth year [Table 1]. The mean global score for perception of educational environment in this study was $102.4/200$ (51.2%) which the study tool, DREEM interprets as more positive than negative perception of educational environment among the respondents. In the evaluation of the scores of individual five domains, we found that two of these are in need of improvement in Ebonyi State University medical school. They are students' perception of course organizers (SPCO) and students' perception of their atmosphere (SPA). The scores of these domains were $20.9/44$ (47.6%) and $16.4/48$ (34.2%) respectively [Tables 3 and 6]. According to DREEM questionnaire assessment, the course organizers (SPCO) need retraining and they are issues needing attention in the learning environment (SPA). For instance, 34.9% of the respondents reported that "our teachers make fun of their students" and 46.5% of them said "our teachers get angry in teaching session"[Table 3]. The study also revealed that 43% of medical students were not usually relaxed during ward teaching [Table 6].

The scores for students' academic self perception (SASP), students' perception of learning (SPL) and students' social self perception (SSSP) were positive with values of $20.7/32$ (64.6%), $27.7/48$ (57.8%) and $16.6/28$ (51.8%) respectively [Tables 2,4,5]. However, SSSP need some attention as 64% of study participants reported that there is no good support system for stressed students, and 33.1% reported that they were too tired to enjoy the course [Table 4].

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics

Variables	Frequency, n=344	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	183	53.2
Female	161	46.8
Age (years)		
18-20	86	25.0
21-23	151	43.9
24-26	83	24.1
27-29	18	5.2
≥30	6	1.7
Mean (SD)	22.4 (±2.9)	
Year of Study		
2nd Year	67	19.5
3rd Year	95	27.6
4th Year	65	18.9
5th Year	51	14.8
6th Year	66	19.2

Table 2: Students' perception of learning (SPL)

Items	SA	A	U	D	SD
I am encouraged to participate in class	105	131	66	28	14
Teaching is often stimulating	65	165	55	42	17
Teaching is student centered	52	101	112	56	23
The teaching helps to develop any competence	74	159	72	32	7
The teaching is well focused	41	116	98	69	20
The teaching helps me to develop confidence	66	139	77	47	15
The teaching time is put to good use	48	143	101	38	14
The teaching overemphasizes factual learning**	40	142	112	46	4
I am clear about the learning objectives of the course	57	151	86	34	16
The teaching discourages me to be an active learner.	26	54	66	138	60
Long term learning is overemphasized over short term	54	114	120	35	21
The teaching is too teacher centered **	51	85	130	63	15
Mean score percentage of SPL = 27.7/48 (57.8%)					

** Negative items were reversely scored; strongly agree (SA), agree (A), unsure (U), disagree (D), strongly disagree (SD)

Table 3: Students' perception of course organizers (SPCO)

Items	SA	A	U	D	SD
Our teachers are knowledgeable	110	195	23	12	4
Our teachers are patient with students	17	132	107	66	22
Our teachers make fun of their students**	20	100	76	127	21
Our teachers are strict and controlling**	45	123	96	76	4
Our teachers appear to have effective communication skills with students	27	155	87	63	12
Our teachers are good at providing feedback to students.	17	122	121	74	10
Our teachers provide constructive criticism	16	138	112	62	16
Our teachers give clear examples.	30	196	74	36	8
Our teachers get angry in teaching session**	34	126	93	72	19
Our teachers are well prepared for their classes	36	166	96	34	12
The students initiate and annoy the teachers	29	97	126	58	34
Mean score percentage of SPCO = 20.9/44 (47.6%)					

** Negative items were reversely scored; strongly agree (SA), agree (A), unsure (U), disagree (D), strongly disagree (SD)

Table 4: Students' social self-perception (SSSP)

Items	SA	A	U	D	SD
There is a good support system for students who get stressed	8	25	91	86	134
I am too tired to enjoy this course**	27	101	77	104	35
I am rarely bored in this course	14	100	78	103	49
I have good friends in this school	93	184	57	8	2
My school life is good	39	153	105	37	10
I seldom feel lonely	35	158	65	72	14
My accommodation is pleasant	54	163	63	46	18
Mean score percentage of SSSP = 16.6/28 (51.8%)					

** Negative item was reversely scored; strongly agree (SA), agree (A), unsure (U), disagree (D), strongly disagree (SD)

Table 5: Students' academic self-perception (SASP)

Items	SA	A	U	D	SD
Learning strategies which worked for me before continue to work for me now	51	134	60	83	16
I am confident about passing this year/session/class	120	152	54	4	14
I feel I am being prepared for my profession	102	153	71	10	8
Last year's work was good preparation for this year's work	57	136	115	32	4
I am able to memorize all I need	34	126	109	65	10
I have learned a lot about empathy in my profession	53	160	101	28	2
My problem solving skill are being well developed	56	168	92	24	2
Much of what I have to learn seems relevant to my career in healthcare	106	171	47	16	4
Mean score percentage of SASP = 20.7/32 (64.6%)					

Strongly agree (SA), agree (A), unsure (U), disagree (D), strongly disagree (SD)

Table 6: Students' perception of atmosphere (SPA)

Items	SA	A	U	D	SD
The atmosphere is relaxed during ward teaching	8	86	102	72	76
This school is well trained	21	78	91	103	51
Cheating is a problem in this school**	68	103	96	59	18
The atmosphere is relaxed during class teaching	15	59	105	91	74
Here are opportunities for me to develop inter personal skills	25	121	87	67	44
I feel comfortable in teaching sessions socially	13	136	104	60	31
The atmosphere is relaxed during tutorials	33	158	72	52	29
I find the experience disappointing**	28	84	104	103	25
I am able to concentrate well	24	149	98	55	18
The enjoyment outweighs the stress of the course	21	42	85	98	96
The atmosphere motivates me as a learner	15	72	85	99	73
I feel able to ask questions I want	20	112	88	76	48
Mean score percentage of SPA = 16.4/48 (34.2%)					

** Negative items were reversely scored; strongly agree (SA), agree (A), unsure (U), disagree (D), strongly disagree (SD)

DISCUSSION

The mean global perception score for educational environment in this study was 51.2%. This, according to the grading formula of DREEM questionnaire indicates more positive than negative perception of education environment. This shows the score is within acceptable limits to DREEM estimation. Similar findings were also found in studies done in Makurdi⁹ and Iran¹⁰ with mean perception scores of 53.2% and 49.8% respectively. Others are Ilorin Nigeria (54.2%)³, Kuwait (53.5%)¹¹, India (53%)¹² and Riyadh (45%)¹³. The low score observed in this study and others could be due to the use of traditional system of medical education. Studies have reported that medical schools in which traditional system is predominant tend to have students' perception score of less than 60%.¹⁴ We found low mean global score for educational environment in our study which could be due to ongoing use of traditional method. This could be improved upon by combining with innovative curriculum or complete replacement by it. The low score we found was influenced by SPCO and SPA subscales in the DREEM questionnaire with scores of 47.6% and 34.2% respectively.

In the SPCO subscale, students were ridiculed by course organizers by making fool of their students, being strict and controlling as well as being irritable (teachers get angry easily in teaching session). These similar findings were also reported in a study in Ilorin, Kwara State Nigeria³. Students see the ridicule issues as humiliating and form of abuse.^{15,16} There is an overall negative outcome since the negative responses impact negatively on the students' ability to fully participate in classroom and ward teaching discussion. Change of attitude by course organizers can improve students' learning, teacher-student interaction and educational environment perception. The medical school authorities should organize workshops to retrain teachers regularly.

We found that students' anxiety resulting in low SPA was centered on the perception that atmosphere was hostile during ward teachings. The experience in school was disappointing which leads to stress of medical profession outweighing the enjoyment.

Studies have shown that workload in medical education exposes students to a lot of pressures which may result in stress.^{17,18} The educational environment if devoid of needless pressure which also entails convenient lecture and ward demonstration will reduce stress on medical students. Improved planning of academic program by management of medical schools will also help to achieve quality education in our medical school.

We observed that slightly above average of SSSP score in this study (51.8%) which centered on non-provision of good support system when stressed as reported by 64% of the respondents. The complaint by the students of lack of good support system was also a major factor in the low SSSP score in studies in Ilorin and Saudi Arabia.^{3,20} However, slightly low SSSP score in this study and low SSSP scores in Ilorin and Saudi Arabia studies were in contrast to that reported in a similar study carried out in Pakistan (58.2%).²¹

This study recorded positive perception for SASP (64.6%) and SPL (57.8%). This is similar to findings in a study carried out in Ilorin with SASP as 68.1% and SPL as 58.8%.³ Improvement is still needed in these aspects of the educational environment. The learning environment impacts majorly on students' learning outcome whether intellectually or socially. Thus improvement is needed in teacher-student interaction, teacher preparedness and teaching methodology and infrastructural development including accommodation. There should also be adequate support for students' psychological and emotional needs. The data were self-reported by the medical students which might have introduced some bias in the perceptions of their educational environment. This was controlled by discussing with them the consequences of providing inaccurate information to the study outcome. They were assured of absolute confidentiality of information provided and non-disclosure. The study was carried out only in one medical school in a Nigerian University and this may limit the extent to which the findings can be generalized to the wider population.

CONCLUSION

Though medical students at Ebonyi State University Abakaliki Nigeria have more positive than negative perception of their educational environment according to DREEM study tool; they could still benefit from improved teaching methodology, improved teacher-student interactions and infrastructural development. Such improvements will help in addressing noted deficiencies in SPCO and SPA. We therefore recommend medical school authorities to identify problem areas at curricular or institutional level and make necessary changes which can result to significant improvement in the learning environment, and therefore students' performance as well as their mental and social being.

Source of funding None.

Conflict of interest - The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

Authors' contributions - BII conceptualized and designed the study. ACO, SBA and CON collected the data. BII analyzed and interpreted the data. BII, EUN, ACO, SBA and CON wrote the manuscript. All authors have critically reviewed and approved the final draft of the manuscript.

Abbreviations **DREEM**, Dundee Ready Education Environment Measure; **SASP**, Students' Academic Self Perception; **SPA**, Students' Perception of Atmosphere; **SPCO**, Students' Perception of Course Organizers; **SPL**, Students' Perception of Learning; **SSSP**, Students' Social Self Perception.

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